

Wireless Time-triggered Federated Learning with Adaptive Local Training Optimization

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Abstract—Traditional synchronous and asynchronous federated learning suffer from limitations, such as straggler, high communication overhead, and model staleness problems. As a generalization of the former two, time-triggered federated learning (TT-Fed) offers a new perspective to alleviate these problems and provides better trade-off between communication and training efficiencies. In this paper, we consider the dynamic aggregation frequency optimization problem under constrained system resources for TT-Fed. We analyze how the number of local training epochs affects the performance of TT-Fed and quantify the impacts of distributed data heterogeneity and model staleness heterogeneity to its convergence upper bound. Based on the derived upper bound, we propose an adaptive local training optimization algorithm to minimize the system loss under constrained resource budget. Numerical simulations show that compared to TT-Fed with fixed number of local training epochs, our proposed adaptive optimization algorithm can provide near optimal results under different degrees of non-IID data distributions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional data-driven machine learning applications face user data privacy and ownership challenges. As a promising paradigm, federated learning (FL) addresses the above problems by coordinating users’ computation capabilities to learn a shared model while keeping their data on devices. First proposed in [1], the state-of-the-art federated averaging (FedAvg) algorithm was known as a type of synchronous (Sync) FL. In FedAvg, all local updates from participated users will be aggregated and used to generate a new global model which will be used in the next iteration. Users are synchronized at the beginning of each iteration, hence the name Sync FL. This type of FL has proven to be communication efficient, but the existence of stragglers highly slows down its convergence speed. To solve this issue, asynchronous (Async) FL was proposed [2], where users do not need to wait for each other to begin their next iteration. However, this setting is highly communication-inefficient and can lead to new problems like model aging, computation bias, and etc [3].

To combine the advantages of the former two and reduce their performance defects, a time-triggered FL algorithm (TT-

Fed) was proposed in [4]. TT-Fed is the generalization form of both Sync FL and Async FL, and provides good trade-off between training and communication efficiencies. In TT-Fed, users are clustered into small tiers to perform training, which can alleviate the straggler issue and control the communication overhead within a small range. The time-triggered aggregation setting at the server side can also provide more robust performance than its event-triggered counterpart FedAT [5].

When it comes to the application of FLs in wireless networks, the complexity of wireless environment has imposed higher demand on system design. In this regard, current research focuses on two aspects: 1) the instability of wireless communication; 2) the scarcity of wireless resources. To deal with the instability of wireless transmission, authors in [4, 6] analyzed the influence of transmission error on FL algorithm’s convergence and designed joint user scheduling and resource allocation algorithms to minimize training loss. Authors in [7] designed a fair aggregation weighting policy to alleviate the model bias induced by transmission errors. Interference from adjacent cells was considered in [8] to design a resource allocation strategy to minimize training loss. For researches dealing with limited wireless resource budgets, the mainly considered system resources include time [8–10], energy [11], and etc. To minimize energy consumption, authors in [11] designed a closed-form policy to optimize power and computation frequency allocation. In [8, 9], authors considered constrained training time budget, and jointly designed the user scheduling and resource allocation scheme accordingly.

However, the above works only considered the fixed number of local training epochs as system parameter during FL’s training process. Whereas, it was shown in [12] that the number of local training epoch setting has great impact on FL’s performance, especially when user data distributions are non-IID. Since users’ data distributions remain unknown to the server during the training, it is non-trivial to discuss the adaptive selection of local training epochs. In [13], the authors proposed a dynamic aggregation frequency selection scheme to reduce resource consumption without considering non-IID user data distribution. Starting from theoretical convergence analysis, authors in [10] proposed an adaptive Sync FL scheme to dynamically choose the number of local training epochs during the training, and non-IID user data was also considered.

We carry out our work on the basis of [10], and we extended

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its Sync FL setting into a more generalized TT-Fed framework. Our key contributions include

- We propose an adaptive local training optimization algorithm for time-triggered federated learning, which is the generalization of both Sync and Async FL algorithms. The proposed algorithm can dynamically configure the number of local training epochs to adapt to different user data distributions under limited system resources.
- We conduct convergence analysis to reveal how the number of local training epochs affects the convergence upper bound of TT-Fed. We quantify how user's data heterogeneity and model staleness heterogeneity affect the convergence accuracy of TT-Fed.
- We evaluate the performance of our proposed adaptive optimization algorithm in comparisons with benchmarks using fixed local training epochs under different data distributions. Our numerical simulations demonstrate that our proposed algorithm can obtain near optimal result and is robust to different degrees of data heterogeneity.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a wireless network, in which a set of users $\mathcal{U} = \{1, 2, \dots, U\}$ and an edge server jointly perform federated learning as shown in Fig. 1. Let us denote $\mathcal{D}_u \triangleq \{x_{u,i} \in \mathbb{R}^I, y_{u,i} \in \mathbb{R}^O\}_{i=1}^{D_u}$ as the data set collected by the u -th user, where $D_u = |\mathcal{D}_u|$, $x_{u,i}$ is the i -th input feature vector, and $y_{u,i}$ is the corresponding ground truth. The goal of iterative FL training process is to find a global model parameter w^* that minimizes the training loss in the whole system, i.e.,

$$w^* = \arg \min_{w \in \mathbb{R}^I} \{F(w) \triangleq \frac{1}{D} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} D_u f_u(w)\}, \quad (1)$$

where $D \triangleq \sum_{u \in \mathcal{U}} D_u$ is the total number of data samples in the whole network, $f_u(w) \triangleq \frac{1}{D_u} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}_u} f(w; x_{u,i}, y_{u,i})$ is the u -th user's local loss function. $f(w; x_{u,i}, y_{u,i})$ is the loss function defined on the data sample $(x_{u,i}, y_{u,i})$ that captures the prediction error using model parameter w .

A. Time-triggered Federated Learning Algorithm

We consider time-triggered federated learning (TT-Fed) in the training process, which is a generalized form of traditional Async and Sync FLs [4]. TT-Fed has two unique characteristics: 1) time-triggered global aggregation, where aggregation at the edge server is triggered at every duration parametrized by ΔT^1 ; 2) user clustering, where users are partitioned into small tiers according to their computation capabilities, channel conditions, and etc². Let us denote $\mathcal{M} \triangleq \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$ as the tier index set in the system, and the user set in the m -th tier as \mathcal{S}_m . The tier index of a user represents its uploading frequency. As shown in Fig. 2, user 3 in tier 2 ($m = 2$) uploads its local

¹ ΔT can be chosen based on users' computation capabilities and the number of training epochs [4].

²User clustering can be done at the server side by a specific tiering module based on user's profile [5].

Fig. 1. The architecture of wireless federated learning.

Fig. 2. Work-flow of TT-Fed with dynamic local training epoch optimization.

model every two rounds, while user 1 and 2 in tier 1 ($m = 1$) upload their models in every training round.

TT-Fed iteratively solves (1) by repeating the following procedures at each round $k \in \mathcal{K}, \mathcal{K} \triangleq \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$:

1) At the beginning of round k , users in set $\{\mathcal{S}_m | (k-1) \bmod m = 0, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}\}$ ³ receive the current global model w_G^{k-1} from the edge server and use it to initialize their local models.

2) Users in step 1) perform N epochs of training using gradient descent based on their local data sets on parallel. Due to the difference of uploading frequency, user $u \in \mathcal{S}_m$ will upload its current local training result in the $(k-1+m)$ -th round. Let us denote $w_{L,u}^{k-1+m}(N)$ as the u -th user's local update after N steps of local gradient descent to be uploaded in round $(k-1+m)$, and define $w_{L,u}^{k-1+m}(0) \triangleq w_G^{k-1}$ to be the initialization model obtained from the server. Then we have local update rule for user $u \in \mathcal{S}_m$ given by

$$w_{L,u}^{k-1+m}(n) = w_{L,u}^{k-1+m}(n-1) - \lambda \nabla f_u[w_{L,u}^{k-1+m}(n-1)], \quad (2)$$

³Users from tier m will upload their local updates every m rounds at training round k satisfying $k \bmod m = 0$, where \bmod denotes the modulo operation. Therefore, users that completed their uploading in the $(k-1)$ -th round is given by set $\{\mathcal{S}_m | (k-1) \bmod m = 0, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}\}$

where λ is the learning rate, and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N$.

3) Before the end of round k , users in set $\{\mathcal{S}_m | k \bmod m = 0, \forall m \in \mathcal{M}\}$ will complete their local computation and upload their local models $w_{L,u}^k(N)$ to the server. The uploaded local models from the same tier m are aggregated first to form the intra-tier model $w_{I,m}^k$, according to

$$w_{I,m}^k = \frac{1}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u w_{L,u}^k(N), \quad (3)$$

where $D_m \triangleq \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u$ is the total number of data samples in the m -th tier. Then, intra-tier models are aggregated to generate a new global model, based on

$$w_G^k = \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbb{1}\{k \bmod m = 0\} \alpha_m w_{I,m}^k + \sum_{m=1}^M (1 - \mathbb{1}\{k \bmod m = 0\}) \alpha_m w_G^{k-1}, \quad (4)$$

where α_m is the aggregation weight for tier m .

The new global model w_G^k is then distributed through downlink to users at training round $k+1$ as shown in Fig. 1, and the above steps 1) - 3) are repeated until termination condition is satisfied.

B. Problem Formulation

In (2), the total number of local training epochs N is configurable. As shown in Fig. 2, training round 1 and 2 use parameter setting $N_1 = 3$ (i.e., users in these training rounds will conduct 3 epochs of local training before uploading their updates), while $N_2 = 5$ in training round 3 and 4. We also note that this parameter change happens every 2 rounds in Fig. 2. This is because there are 2 user tiers in total in Fig. 2, and users in different tiers can complete their local training before the end of the same round in every two rounds. Let us denote $lcm(M)$ as the least common multiple of the tier indices in the network $\{1, 2, \dots, M\}$. Therefore, the parameter reconfiguration should happen every $lcm(M)$ rounds to enable users' parameter reconfiguration to be aligned.

The purpose of parameter dynamic configuration is to make the best use of wireless resources to optimize FL performance. It has been shown in [10] and [12] that fixed setting for local training epochs is not optimal under different data distributions. Since data sharing is forbidden in FL, data distributions among users should be inferred dynamically through the training process.

Let us denote l as the resource consumed by conducting a single epoch of local training at each user side, and g as the resource consumed by conducting one step of global aggregation. Assume FL goes through K rounds of training before termination. Then, under resource budget R , we aim to solve for K and N to minimize system loss:

$$(P1) \quad \min_{K, N} F(w_G^K) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad K(g + Nl) \leq R. \quad (5a)$$

Fig. 3. Relationships among model parameters used in convergence analysis.

Directly solving (P1) is difficult, since the analytical expression of the optimization goal is unclear. We need to properly transform the optimization goal into tractable expressions and analyze the impacts of variables to finally solve it.

III. CONVERGENCE ANALYSIS

We resort to convergence analysis of TT-Fed to find out how the values of N and K impact the algorithm's performance. We derive the upper bound of $F(w_G^K) - F(w^*)$ and use it as approximation to solve problem (P1).

A. Definitions and Assumptions

We first introduce an auxiliary vector $v^k(n)$, $\forall k \in \mathcal{K}$, $\forall n \in [0, N]$ which synchronizes with w_G^{k-1} at the beginning of the k -th round, i.e., $v^k(0) = w_G^{k-1}$. $v^k(n)$ is the model parameter, which follows centralized gradient descent updating rule given by

$$v^k(n+1) = v^k(n) - \lambda \nabla \tilde{F}^k[v^k(n)], \quad (6)$$

where we define $\tilde{F}^k[w]$ as the updating loss function at the k -th round $\tilde{F}^k[w] \triangleq \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbb{1}\{k \bmod m = 0\} \alpha_m F_m[w]$, and $F_m[w] \triangleq \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u f_u[w]}{D_m}$ denotes the tier loss function of the m -th tier. The updating loss function $\tilde{F}^k[w]$ comes from the sum of tier loss functions $F_m[w]$ weighted by α_m . Compared to the global loss function $F[w]$, only users who will upload their local models to the server at the k -th training round are considered into the updating loss function, i.e., $\{u \in \mathcal{S}_m | k \bmod m = 0, m \in \mathcal{M}\}$.

We also define $\tilde{w}_G^k(n)$ to be the possible global aggregation result after $n \in [0, N]$ steps of local gradient descent at the k -th training round. According to this definition, we have $\tilde{w}_G^k(0) = w_G^{k-1}$, since the result of the $(k-1)$ -th aggregation w_G^{k-1} will be broadcast to ready users at the beginning of the k -th round as their initialization model. Moreover, it is straightforward to see that $\tilde{w}_G^k(N) = w_G^k$. The relationships among $v^k(n)$, $\tilde{w}_G^k(n)$ and w_G^k are shown in Fig. 3.

Assumption 1 To serve the tractability of convergence analysis, the following assumptions are made:

- For $\forall u \in \mathcal{U}$, the local loss function $f_u(w)$ is convex.
- $f_u(w)$ is ρ -Lipschitz, i.e., $\forall x, y \in \text{dom}(f_u)$, $\|f_u(y) - f_u(x)\| \leq \rho\|y - x\|$.
- $f_u(w)$ is β -smooth, i.e., $\forall x, y \in \text{dom}(f_u)$, $\|\nabla f_u(y) - \nabla f_u(x)\| \leq \beta\|y - x\|$.
- Bounded global model change between two consecutive aggregations, i.e., $\|w_G^{k-1} - w_G^k\| \leq C$.

To characterize the non-IID data distributions of users, we have the following definitions:

Definition 1 (Local-Updating Gradient Divergence) For an updating user u at the k -th aggregation satisfying $\{u \in \mathcal{S}_m | k \bmod m = 0\}$, define δ_u as an upper bound of $\|\nabla f_u(w) - \nabla \tilde{F}^k(w)\|$, i.e.,

$$\|\nabla f_u(w) - \nabla \tilde{F}^k(w)\| \leq \delta_u, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (7)$$

Definition 2 (Updating-Global Gradient Similarity) We use the following inequalities to characterize the similarity of $\nabla \tilde{F}^k(w)$ and $\nabla F(w)$, i.e.:

$$\nabla \tilde{F}^k(w)^\top \nabla F(w) \geq \sigma \|\nabla F(w)\|^2, \quad (8)$$

$$\|\nabla \tilde{F}^k(w)\|^2 \leq \nu \|\nabla F(w)\|^2, \nu > 0, \quad (9)$$

where σ and ν are measurement parameters.

B. Convergence Upper Bound

We follow similar convergence upper bound derivation steps as used in [10]. We first give the global loss gap between $F[w_G^k]$ and $F[v^k(n)]$ upper bounded by the following theorem.

Theorem 1 For an M -tier TT-Fed framework with N steps of local gradient descent, we have

$$F[w_G^k] - F[v^k(N)] \leq \rho h^k(N), \quad (10)$$

where $h^k(N)$ is given by

$$h^k(N) = \underbrace{\left[\frac{(\lambda\beta + 1)^N - 1}{\beta} - \lambda N \right]}_{\text{Distributed Data Heterogeneity}} \delta^k + \underbrace{\sum_{m=1}^M \mathbb{1}\{k \bmod m = 0\} \alpha_m C(m-1) [(\lambda\beta + 1)^N - 1]}_{\text{Model Staleness Heterogeneity}}, \quad (11)$$

and for simplicity we denote

$$\delta^k \triangleq \sum_{m=1}^M \mathbb{1}\{k \bmod m = 0\} \frac{\alpha_m}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u \delta_u. \quad (12)$$

Proof. We first derive upper bound for $\|w_{L,u}^k(n) - v^k(N)\|, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$, then use the relationships between w_G^k and $w_{L,u}^k(n)$ to yield the result. Due to space limitation, the detailed proof is omitted. \square

Remark 1 It can be seen from Theorem 1 that the difference between $F[w_G^k]$ and $F[v^k(N)]$ at the k -th round comes from two parts: 1) **Model Staleness Heterogeneity**, where updates

from different tiers with different degrees of staleness adds to the heterogeneity of model training; 2) **Distributed Data Heterogeneity**, where local updates based on non-IID local data sets make the aggregation result deviate from centralized updates. When $M = 1, N = 1$, TT-Fed transforms to FedAvg with single step of local gradient descent. Under such circumstance, we have $h^k(N) = 0$, meaning that the distributed update of w_G^k is equivalent to centralized update of $v^k(N)$ even the local data set is non-IID, i.e., $\delta_u > 0$. This result is compatible with the results of Theorem 1 in [10]. When $M = 1, \delta_u = 0, \forall u \in \mathcal{U}$, TT-Fed transforms to FedAvg with IID local data set. In this case, we can still have $h^k(N) = 0$ even when $N > 1$, meaning that we can set large number of local training steps N to reduce communication overhead without sacrificing system performance. Theorem 1 also tells us that having too many tiers, i.e., large M , in the system is harmful to the training process since it magnifies the impact of Model Staleness Heterogeneity. Therefore, even partitioning users into small tiers can help alleviate the straggler issues commonly found in Sync FL, we should carefully tune the trade-off between system performance and training efficiency.

Based on Theorem 1, the convergence upper bound of TT-Fed is given by Theorem 2.

Theorem 2 When the following conditions are satisfied: 1) $0 < \lambda \leq \frac{2\sigma}{\beta\nu}$; 2) $\lambda\xi N(\sigma - \frac{\beta\nu\lambda}{2}) - \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2} > 0, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$; 3) $F[v^k(N)] - F[w^*] \geq \varepsilon, \forall k \in \mathcal{K}$, for some $\varepsilon > 0$; for TT-Fed with N steps of local gradient descent, the convergence upper bound between $F[w_G^k]$ and $F(w^*)$ is given by

$$F[w_G^k] - F[w^*] \leq \frac{1}{\lambda K N (\sigma - \frac{\beta\nu\lambda}{2}) - \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}}, \quad (13)$$

where $\xi \triangleq \min_{k,n} \frac{1}{\|v^k(n) - w^*\|^2}$.

Proof. We first analyze the convergence of $F[v^k(N)]$. Then, according to the gap between $F[v^k(N)]$ and $F[w_G^k]$, convergence upper bound of $F[w_G^k] - F[w^*]$ can be obtained. Due to space limitation, the detailed proof is omitted. \square

Remark 2 Since $h^k(N) \geq 0$, to minimize the convergence upper bound in Theorem 2 requires us to increase the value of the term $\lambda\xi K N \sigma$, while decreasing $\lambda\xi K N \frac{\beta\nu\lambda}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}$. Given the values of K and N , we need to increase σ , while decreasing ν and $h^k(N)$. According to (8) and (9), a large value of σ and a small value of ν imply that the gradient of updating loss function should be similar to the global loss function. Based on Theorem 1, we know that to minimize $h^k(N)$, one need to reduce both the *Model Staleness Heterogeneity* and the *Distributed Data Heterogeneity*. Under unlimited system resource (e.g., training time, energy consumption etc), it is straightforward to see that setting $M = 1, N = 1$ can achieve the best model performance. However, due to the computation heterogeneity of users, ΔT under such case will be very large which prolongs the time needed for convergence. This highlights the necessity of adaptive control under limited system resource.

Algorithm 1 TT-Fed with Adaptive Local Training Optimization

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1: Initialize  $w_G^0$  to be random vector,  $k = 0$ ,  $N = 1$ 
2: for  $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$  do
3:   Server transmit current global model  $w_G^{k-1}$  to users in
   tier  $m \in \mathcal{M}$ , satisfying  $\{m | (k-1) \bmod m = 0\}$ 
4:   Use user profile to calculate training round duration
    $\Delta T(N)$ 
5:   for each user  $u$  in  $\{\mathcal{S}_m | (k-1) \bmod m = 0\}$  in parallel
   do
6:     Record  $k_u = k - 1$ , receive  $w_G^{k_u}$ 
7:     Initialize local model  $w_{L,u}^{k_u+m}(0) = w_G^{k_u}$ 
8:     Conduct  $N$  steps of local training using (2)
9:     Send  $w_{L,u}^{k_u+m}(N)$  to server at training round  $k_u+m$ 
10:    if  $k \bmod lcm(M) = m$  then
11:      Calculate  $\hat{\rho}_u = \frac{\|f_u(w_G^{k-m}) - f_u(w_{L,u}^k(N))\|}{\|w_G^{k-m} - w_{L,u}^k(N)\|}$ ,
       $\hat{\beta}_u = \frac{\|\nabla f_u(w_G^{k-m}) - \nabla f_u(w_{L,u}^k(N))\|}{\|w_G^{k-m} - w_{L,u}^k(N)\|}$ 
12:      Record  $\nabla \tilde{f}_u = \nabla f_u(w_G^{k-m})$ 
13:    end if
14:    if  $k \bmod lcm(M) = 0$  then
15:      Send  $\hat{\rho}_u, \hat{\beta}_u$  and  $\nabla f_u(w_G^{k-lcm(M)})$  to server
16:    end if
17:  end for
18:  Server receive  $w_{L,u}^k(N)$  from users and perform
  aggregation according to (3) and (4)
19:  if  $k \bmod lcm(M) = 0$  then
20:    Receive  $\hat{\rho}_u, \hat{\beta}_u$  and  $\nabla f_u(w_G^{k-lcm(M)})$  from user
21:    Estimate  $\hat{\beta} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\alpha_m}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u \delta_u \hat{\beta}_u$  and
     $\hat{\rho} = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\alpha_m}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u \delta_u \hat{\rho}_u$ 
22:    Denote  $k_0 = k - lcm(M)$ , and calculate
     $\nabla F(w_G^{k_0}) = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\alpha_m}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u \nabla f_u(w_G^{k_0})$ 
23:    Estimate  $\hat{\delta}_u = \|\nabla F(w_G^{k_0}) - \nabla f_u(w_G^{k_0})\|$  for each
    user, and estimate  $\delta^k = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\alpha_m}{D_m} \sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_m} D_u \delta_u$ 
24:    Calculate  $\nabla F_1(w_G^{k_0}) = \frac{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_1} D_u \nabla f_u(w_G^{k_0})}{\sum_{u \in \mathcal{S}_1} D_u}$ 
25:    Estimate  $\hat{\sigma} = \frac{\nabla F_1(w_G^{k_0})^\top \nabla F(w_G^{k_0})}{\|\nabla F(w_G^{k_0})\|^2}$ ,
     $\hat{\nu} = \frac{\|\nabla F_1(w_G^{k_0})\|^2}{\|\nabla F(w_G^{k_0})\|^2}$ ,  $\hat{C} = \|w_G^{k-1} - w_G^k\|$ 
26:    Use line search to obtain new value of  $N$  within
    range of  $\{1, \dots, N_{\max}\}$  according to (15).
27:  end if
28: end for

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IV. LOCAL TRAINING OPTIMIZATION ALGORITHM

Since the optimum loss $F[w^*]$ is a fixed unknown value, minimizing $F(w_G^k)$ in (5) equals to minimize the convergence upper bound given by (13). However, the term $\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}$ in (13) requires us to know all $h^k(N), k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ ahead of time at a random round k , which is impossible since the training for $k' > k$ is undone yet. We solve this problem myopically by considering $h^k(N)$ at current round k is used in the whole training procedure, and $\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2} \approx K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}$.

Thus, we can approximately solve (P1) by

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\text{P}_k) \quad & \min_{K, N} \frac{1}{\lambda \xi K N (\sigma - \frac{\beta \nu \lambda}{2}) - K \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}} \quad (14) \\
 & \text{s.t.} \quad K(g + Nl) \leq R. \quad (14a)
 \end{aligned}$$

We can see that the optimization goal in (14) decreases with K , and thus its optimum is obtained at $K = \lfloor \frac{R}{g + Nl} \rfloor$, where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the rounding down function. Substituting this into (14), solving (P_k) equals to find

$$N^* = \arg \max_{N=1,2,\dots} \lfloor \frac{R}{g + Nl} \rfloor [\lambda \xi N (\sigma - \frac{\beta \nu \lambda}{2}) - \frac{\rho h^k(N)}{\varepsilon^2}], \quad (15)$$

and hence $K^* = \lfloor \frac{R}{g + lN^*} \rfloor$. Since setting the derivative of (15) to zero yields no closed-form solution, we solve for N^* using line search algorithm similar to [10].

The detailed local training optimization algorithm for TT-Fed is presented in **Algorithm 1**, which enables server to dynamically control the local training epoch setting (N) to adapt to user data distributions⁴.

In steps 1 of **Algorithm 1**, we set initial global model w_G^0 to be random vector and initialize the training round index k and local training epoch value N . Then server distributes the current global model to ready users, and set the training round duration according to N as $\Delta T(N)$ (steps 3-4)⁵. Despite performing local training as in regular FLs after receiving global model from server (steps 5-9), users will estimate and send extra parameters to the server every $lcm(M)$ training rounds. In steps 10-12, users calculate $\hat{\rho}_u$ and $\hat{\beta}_u$ at their first uploading round (i.e., $k \bmod lcm(M) = m$) after server's last reconfiguration, and record the local gradient of the global model obtained after server's last reconfiguration (i.e., $\nabla f_u(w_G^{k-m})$) as $\nabla \tilde{f}_u$. Then, when server performs new reconfiguration in training round k satisfying $k \bmod lcm(M) = 0$, users transmit these parameters to server (steps 14-15). Despite aggregating user updates to generate new global model (step 18), the server performs parameter estimation (We note that the term $\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2}$ in (13) is defined as a control parameter which remain fixed during the training [9, 10]) and reconfigures the value of N every $lcm(M)$ training rounds (steps 19-26).

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We consider a wireless network with $U = 20$ users and an edge server jointly train a feedforward neural network (FNN) using TT-Fed. The FNN has a single hidden layer with 50 neurons and we use cross-entropy loss function during training. Each user has equal sized dataset with 120 data samples from MNIST hand written digits database [14]. The learned FL models are evaluated on the test MNIST dataset. We set the control parameter $\frac{1}{\varepsilon^2} = 10^{-3}$ [9, 10]. Users are clustered into 2 tiers with first ten forming tier 1 and the others forming tier 2. We adopt Dirichlet distribution with

⁴We note that the parameter reconfiguration for N happens every $lcm(M)$ training rounds as discussed in Section II-B.

⁵The value setting of $\Delta T(N)$ can be based on the slowest user's computation capability as shown in [4].

Fig. 4. Test accuracy with different N values in different data distributions.

concentration parameter θ to model the non-IID data behavior of local data sets [15]. When $\theta \rightarrow 0$, a user will randomly hold only one class of data; while when $\theta \rightarrow \infty$, data class ratios on a user will be even (each class with ratio of 0.1).

We consider time as limited resource and set time budget $R = 30$ seconds. Each local training step consumes computation time, while each aggregation consumes transmission time. The time consumption for aggregation and parameter estimation is omitted due to the powerful computation capability of the server and the low complexity of these tasks. We use the same wireless transmission and computation model in [4] Section II - C and E. CPU frequency of users in tier 1 is 2GHz, and 1GHz for those in tier 2. We assume the slowest user's computation time to perform a single step of local training is T . We set training round duration $\Delta T(N)$ to be $0.6NT$ [4], with N being the number of local training epochs. Each user is allocated with 1MHz bandwidth for uplink transmission. The other parameters used in the simulation are the same with those in the simulation part of [4].

Fig. 4 plots the test accuracy under different number of local training epochs N . Each point on the solid lines is the average converged accuracy of 40 different TT-Fed training experiments under the same training data setting with fixed N during the whole training. Take an example as shown in Fig. 4, data points on the solid black line are the converged results of TT-Fed trainings fixing different values of N ($10^0 \sim 10^2$) under the data distribution $\theta = 0.01$. The single marker with the same color shows the average local training epochs N selected by our proposed algorithm and its converged accuracy. It can be seen from Fig. 4 that our proposed adaptive N control algorithm yields a result that is close to the optimal point under the four different data distribution cases. It is also interesting to see that when data distribution is highly non-IID ($\theta = 0.01, 1$), the optimum N values are smaller than those under more evenly distributed data cases ($\theta = 50, 100$). This is because local training updates in non-IID data cases will deviate much more from each other under large N value

than that in IID cases, and thus large N value setting is even harmful to the algorithm performance, which is in line with what we know from Theorem 2 and [12]. This also validates the effectiveness of our proposed control algorithm.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we proposed an adaptive local training optimization algorithm for time-triggered FL (TT-Fed). We formulated the problem of local training epoch number optimization for TT-Fed under resource constrained wireless networks. Then, we solve this problem by resorting to convergence analysis and proper approximations. Finally, we give the detailed steps of our proposed local training optimization algorithm. Our numerical results show that our proposed adaptive control algorithm can obtain near optimal results compared to benchmarks with fixed local training epochs under different data settings.

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